

JUPYTER NOTEBOOKS FOR PROVIDING ACCESS TO DIGITIZED AND BORN-DIGITAL COLLECTIONS

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Abstract – There are often significant barriers to accessing and using collections as data in the GLAM sector. Jupyter Notebooks are an increasingly popular form of hybrid tooling that combines data and code to make digital collections more accessible, particularly for less technical users. This workshop will help participants explore digitised and born-digital collections using Jupyter Notebooks developed by several GLAM institutions. Expert facilitators will ensure users discover the possibilities that Notebooks offer. The opportunities for the audience will be two-fold – to focus on working with data, but also to give insights and experience into developing their own Notebooks. We will also provide use cases and a discussion on the preservation challenges of the notebooks.

Submission Type – Workshop.

Keywords – Access, Born Digital Content, Digitised Content, Jupyter Notebook, Computational Access.

Conference Topics – Tūtaki – Encounter.

I. COLLECTIONS AS DATA

GLAM institutions dedicate large quantities of resources to collecting born-digital material and

digitising physical collections. While each of these materials are valuable in their own right, there is also significant research potential when viewed as data. Cultural heritage institutions have also been gradually offering access to digital collections containing different materials such as metadata, text, and images. Recent methods for providing access to digital collections through initiatives such as “GLAM Labs” (glamlabs.io) and “Collections as Data” (collectionsasdata.github.io) have focused on the adoption and reuse of computational access methods.

Computational access to collections typically requires technical expertise and knowledge, as well as access and use of appropriate IT infrastructure [1]. These are common barriers to researchers and other users in realizing the potential of digital collections. While the teaching and use of technical skills in interrogating digital collections is becoming more commonplace, collecting institutions must grapple with how best to facilitate access to their digital collections in a way that allows and promotes the use of these skills.

II. JUPYTER NOTEBOOKS

In this context, Jupyter Notebooks have emerged as a powerful tool to facilitate meaningful access to the collections. GLAM institutions have started to employ Jupyter Notebooks as a new approach to demonstrate how users can access and experiment with datasets derived from their collections [1]. Projects like the GLAM Workbench [2] illustrate their utility across various types of collections, including both digitized collections and web archives. They offer interactive and reproducible environments for exploring and analyzing collections of data. With built-in support for data visualization libraries and interactive widgets, Jupyter Notebooks make it easier to access and interpret complex datasets, test hypotheses, and share findings collaboratively. There is a flexibility that the Notebooks can provide, that caters to all levels of technical expertise, and allows for an educational experience as well as a workspace for power users. They can be hosted locally on a user's device or on the many hosting providers available online, to take advantage of the extendable computing resources the cloud has to offer.

III. WORKSHOP OUTCOMES

The workshop aims to provide the following outcomes:

- Grow the participants' experience using Jupyter Notebooks.
- Give participants the confidence to explore further datasets using Jupyter Notebooks.
- Teach them how to build on and extend existing Notebooks to meet their needs, and provide tips for building their own.
- Advise on the types and structures of data that work well with Jupyter Notebooks.
- Test purpose-built Jupyter Notebooks on the workshop organizer's data collections.
- Provide use cases and possibilities of Notebooks to inspire future use, and discuss the preservation challenges of the notebooks and research outputs.

IV. WORKSHOP STRUCTURE

The workshop will begin with short presentations on the framework for creating a collection of Jupyter

Notebooks [3], examples based on digitized and born-digital collections, and how to get started using a Jupyter Notebook.

The main part of the workshop will be for participants to use and explore the digital collections with one or more of the Jupyter Notebooks available.

The session will wrap up with a discussion on the preservation challenges of the notebooks.

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